

Subjective assessment by a teacher of his psychological age as a factor contributing to professional longevity and psychological health

 Deulin Dmitry Vladimirovich¹

¹ Faculty of Extreme Psychology, Moscow State University of Psychology and Education, Moscow, Russian Federation

ABSTRACT

Purpose of the study. The problem is linked to trends in education reform, a shortage of teaching staff, and the emergence of numerous risks in the educational environment associated with early teacher burnout and, consequently, dismissal. The study of personal, organizational, socioeconomic, and other factors influencing teachers' subjective perception of their age, psychological health, and professional longevity is an extremely important area of research today. Lack of time, high administrative workload, pressure from responsibility, a toxic school environment, and broader systemic problems negatively impact teacher well-being and lead to significant reductions in their workforce. Younger generations are less engaged in this field, raising the objective challenge of retaining a «core» teaching staff comprised of more experienced teachers. The primary goal of the study is to clarify the relationship between individual «psychological health» scales and «professional longevity» scales. The main sample included teachers from general education organizations, predominantly women, with teaching experience from 24 to 65 years (average age 44±1 years, 32 participants, pilot study).

Materials and Methods. In our study, we used a theoretical analysis of the literature on the problem under study, including a conceptual analysis of previously conducted studies. The empirical methods included: the Scale for Assessing Expected Retirement Age by T.N. Berezina; Self-Assessment of Psychological Age by K.A. Abulkhanova and T.N. Berezina; the Scale of Psychological Well-Being by K. Riff, adapted by N.N. Lepeshinsky. Methods of mathematical processing and analysis of the obtained data: descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, descriptive data analysis, analysis of variance with Fisher's exact test.

Research results. For the first time, the relationships between the professional longevity and psychological health scales of teachers in general education organizations were studied in the context of the digital transformation of educational environments, the reform of the education system, and the training of school teachers. The study identified differences between different age groups of teachers on the following scales: positive relationships; autonomy; environmental management; personal growth; life goals; self-acceptance; and psychological well-being. As teachers gain more teaching experience, they begin to rethink their age. The older the teacher, the older they perceive themselves to be relative to their actual age.

Conclusions. The study shows that the average age of teachers who subjectively assess themselves younger than the real age is 62-63 years. Those who rate themselves older are 57-58 years old. The time interval of subjective aging falls on the period of 45-54 years, possibly due to the onset of stages of professional burnout. Teachers who rate themselves younger have a higher psychological well-being index, primarily due to the «environmental management» scale. The differences between contrasting groups on the following scales are revealed: positive relationships; autonomy; environmental management; personal growth; goals in life; self-acceptance and psychological well-being. As teachers increase their teaching experience, they begin to overestimate their age internally, considering themselves to be older than their real age.

Keywords: psychological health, professional longevity, psychological age, teacher, general education organization, professional burnout, threats and risks in the education system.

Corresponding Author: Deulin Dmitry Vladimirovich, e-mail: ddeulin@yandex.ru

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INTRODUCTION

Contemporary global processes have marked the presence of a crisis in all spheres of society. It is clear how significant psychophysiological resources are needed to overcome stress and anxiety. Technological progress only increases workers' anxiety and undermines their psychological health. This anxiety is primarily driven by the possibility of rapid professional depreciation and the lack of competitive equality with artificial intelligence technologies. Therefore, the need arises for a more detailed study of aspects of the professional longevity of general education teachers, their self-esteem, and their perception of psychological age in relation to psychological well-being and health.

Today, human health and ability to work are recognized by the global community as some of the most significant values. The Constitution of the World Health Organization, adopted in 1946, establishes that the enjoyment of the highest attainable standard of health is one of the fundamental rights of every human being without distinction as to race, religion, political belief, economic or social status.

The State undertakes obligations aimed at respecting, protecting and fulfilling the right to health. Accordingly, States must refrain from interfering directly or indirectly with human health; take measures to prevent such interference by third parties; and take positive measures to enable and facilitate the enjoyment of this right by individuals and communities.

One of the components of human health as a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being of a person, and not only the absence of diseases and physical defects, is a high level of psychological health. A person's full-fledged life activity has always depended on his ability to function productively. And psychological health allows us to provide this mechanism. Considering this circumstance, it is important to note that the problem of psychological health is becoming extremely important and urgent.

Psychological age, as a complex construct, is considered in the study as part of biopsychological age and draws on the theoretical concept of T.N. Berezina, where this indicator reflects personal maturity/immaturity and is based on a person's subjective assessment of their life path, achievements, and significant events. According to T.N. Berezina, a pattern has been identified: with increasing age, the deficit of resources that reduce risks and threats to an individual's psychological security increases (Finogenova, Berezina, Litvinova, Rybtsov, 2023).

Other studies examine psychological age through L.S. Vygotsky's cultural-historical framework. This phenomenon is examined taking into account the social conditions of development, «leading activity», new psychological conditions, central and auxiliary

developmental factors, and the resolution of age-related crises as a bridge to the next period of development (Solovieva, Quintanar Rojas, 2021). Age is a socially constructed socio-psychological and biological phenomenon. Its content includes the periodization of the life course, the age classification of society, and the systemic approach to the cultural symbolization of this phenomenon. It is the social situation of development that determines age.

Research has noted links between psychological well-being, self-assessed health, and age. Social age is the most strongly correlated component of subjective age with psychological well-being. The relationship between subjective age and psychological well-being is mediated by other phenomena, such as time perspective. Overall, the period of aging and old age is perceived negatively by all age groups. Most people perceive aging as unfavorable, filled with regrets and disappointments, which is a risk factor for further development and preparation for old age (Eidelman, 2021).

Some authors, based on meta-analysis, show that subjective or psychological age, as well as optimism, self-efficacy, life purpose, resilience, tolerance for uncertainty, and other factors, are important factors in a person's psychological well-being (Sergienko, Pavlova, 2024). Certainly, psychological age reflects the degree of psychological well-being and psychological health.

Thus, it can be said that psychological age reflects the degree of psychological well-being, psychological health, and professional longevity. Psychological health and professional longevity are important components of professional self-fulfillment.

The problems of professional longevity and psychological health have been developed in both domestic and foreign scientific research: through education as the most important factor of working capacity (Kim, 2023); studies of predictors of professional longevity (Maltseva and Pozdnyakov, 2023); the influence of value-semantic and spiritual factors on professional longevity (Berezina, 2021; Dominguez et al., 2024, etc.); development of a systematization of factors of professional longevity (Sokolova, 2016); overcoming extreme factors contributing to professional longevity (Goryacheva, 2019); studying the psychological aspects of work capacity in high-risk professions (Viktorov, 2018), etc. The most significant contribution to the development of the problems of «psychological health» was made by such foreign scientists as Maslow, K. Rogers, K. G. Jung. Russian science considered the problems of «psychological health» in the system of psychological safety of the educational environment (Baeva, 2002); a necessary condition for the full functioning and development

of a person in the process of his life (Khukhlaeva, 2017); optimal functioning of all human mental structures (Kashkareva, 2003).

A decrease in human health can affect professional longevity and cause a negative economic effect. The study on work and aging highlights the urgency of the problem of the «slowdown syndrome» in the labor market caused by a decrease in the volume of surplus labor, which has long been one of the main drivers of economic growth. The authors study the evolution of the concept of the «silver tsunami», realities and myths about the ability and success of older workers (Durakova et al., 2025).

The study of the essence and content of the phenomenon of «psychological health» took place within the framework of numerous domestic and foreign scientific studies (O. N. Kuznetsov, N. D. Lakosina, V. I. Lebedev, G. S. Nikiforov, G. K. Ushakov, A. Maslow, A. Ellis, etc.). Psychologists focus on different levels of health: mental, psychological, and social. Regarding the category of personality, the phenomenon of «psychological health» is being studied, which, according to I. V. It is the result of a deep interaction between the development, education and upbringing of children and schoolchildren at each stage of ontogenesis. It has been shown that it is the interaction of these processes that contributes to human development (Dubrovina, 2015).

In some Russian studies related to the study of the psychological safety of the educational environment, it has been shown that a high level of culture of pedagogical activity and pedagogical interaction ensures the mental health of schoolchildren and teachers (Baeva and Semikin, 2005). In more recent studies, psychotechnologies are being developed and proposed that create the psychological safety of the educational environment and are aimed at maintaining the mental health of adolescents (Baeva, 2012).

An important aspect of maintaining psychological health is the image of the teacher, which acts as a health-saving factor in the case of its positive characteristics in the educational process of the school (democratic leadership style, communication style based on passion for joint creative activities, friendly disposition style, appearance, designed in a business style, subject-spatial environment, designed taking into account the recommendations of color therapy, etc. etc.) (Zak, 2017).

L. R. Kashkareva understands psychological health as the optimal functioning of all mental structures of a person necessary for current life activity, dynamic harmony of a person, divided into external (between a person and people around him, nature, space) and internal (physical body, his thoughts and feelings), providing an active dynamic balance between a person and the environment (Kashkareva, 2013).

In foreign psychology, K. Rogers, A. Maslow, K.G. Jung and many other researchers studied psychological health.

A. Maslow proposed «self-actualization» as the main criterion of psychological health, in which a person develops and realizes his potentials. As the author notes, a neurotic and even the average normal person is ready to succumb to feelings of guilt, shame and anxiety, even in cases where it is absolutely not necessary. This fact distinguishes him from a healthy person. The self-actualizing personality is closely related to human needs and values. Their dissatisfaction leads to the formation of neuroses and psychoses. The prerequisites for healthy development are contained in the personality itself, and the body's tendency to grow is determined not only and not so much by the external environment as by its inherent tendency to grow (Maslow, 1987).

K.G. Jung points out that the desire to acquire the integrity of the elements of personality, socio-psychological self, the development and realization of one's «Ego» distinguishes a psychologically healthy personality. According to the author, «Mental health» is manifested through the ability to creatively integrate all aspects of one's experience (C.G. Jung, 1994). K. Rogers considered health from the point of view of freedom and openness to potential experience. And here the main driver is the desire for self-realization of one's inner potential.

It is worth noting that in the historiography of world psychological science, two trends have emerged in the study of personal health: there is a differentiation of the concepts of psychological and mental health. The problem of mental health in Russia is being studied by such scientists as B.S. Bratus, V.E. Pakhalyan, T.N. Metelkina. In our study, we articulated the problem of «psychological health».

A.G. Portnova and M.G. Ivanova explain that the theoretical and methodological works of psychologists present various aspects of the consideration of health. A person is a multifunctional and multilevel system, therefore, health manifests itself at the level of the individual, personality and subject of activity. The authors also take into account the fact that they consider health when analyzing the nature of mental processes, states and manifestations of personality traits, health can be considered an indicator describing personality in all its manifestations (Portnova, Ivanova, 2010).

According to O.V. Khukhlaeva, the construct «psychological health» is a necessary condition for the full functioning and development of a person in the process of his life, allowing him to adequately perform various social and cultural roles. From these positions, psychological health includes the following elements: axiological (personal values, the values

of the «Ego» of other people), instrumental (the ability to reflect) and need-motivational (striving for self-development) components (Khukhlaeva, 2003).

The socio-psychological construction of «professional longevity» is becoming important in the coordinate system of psychological health. Maintaining psychological health is a predictor of ensuring professional longevity, including for teachers of secondary schools. T.N. Berezina's research has shown that the main factor of professional longevity is the state of health (objective and subjective). Having a family and children is important only for women, and they reduce professional longevity. Having interesting hobbies increases professional longevity in women and may decrease it in men. Residence is also a factor that affects professional longevity. Thus, living in a large city reduces professional longevity for both men and women (for women at the trend level) (Berezina, 2025). In studies of the mediation of professional longevity by the «life force» of the same author, it is stated:

- firstly, this phenomenon is considered as a source of any human activity;
- secondly, in the process of professional activity, a person spends his life force; and harder work leads to increased spending, which leads to a reduction in the working age, as well as a reduction in life expectancy.;
- thirdly, there are mechanisms for restoring vitality: socio-economic compensation (higher wages, more affordable medicine, better food, etc.); reduction of energy expenditure and restoration of vitality in a natural way through the optimization of sleep and rest; use of personal resources (physical education, intellectual and creative hobbies, needlework, humor, etc.) and psychological methods of restoring vitality (Berezina, 2025).

Today, «models of excess activity» (V.I. Yasvin), the idea of a «side product that transforms activity» (Ya.A. Ponomarev), «intellectual initiative» (D.B. Bogoyavlenskaya), the nature of «goal formation» (O.K. Tikhomirov), the essence of «personal choice» can also be considered the main directions of research on the problems of personal performance (D.A. Leontiev) and others.

Zotova N.G., together with a team of authors, expresses the opinion that a teacher comes to productive longevity in the profession through a long process of professional development, through understanding the purpose of the profession, realizing their capabilities to master it, and evaluating their current and potential professional abilities (Zotova et al., 2020).

In the work of Bilogo A.M., aspects of maintaining health and professional longevity are studied. The author points out several aspects in his problem field:

- the creation of a comprehensive expert system for personality analysis makes it possible to reliably and validly determine the preferred type of behavior, perception and processing of information of a personality, describe the requirements of an activity and assess the level of internal stress of a personality that arises when performing tasks and responsibilities in various types of activities.;

- identification of the level of psychophysiological stress of a personality that occurs when performing tasks and responsibilities in various types of activities and is determined using a developed expert system that affects the development of psychosomatic disorders and diseases, as well as the development of age-related crises;

- the program of implementing a monitoring system in the organization using the developed expert system and approaches to assessing the psychophysiological stress of a personality that occurs when performing tasks and responsibilities in various types of activities allows maintaining professional health and staff engagement (Bily, 2020)

The increase in the retirement age of employees associated with the ongoing pension reform in Russia should be based on the study of personal, including spiritual and moral factors affecting professional longevity and health. Health is an integrative characteristic of a person, which includes the most diverse spheres of his individual being and life activity. The highest, spiritual level of personal health has a transformative effect on the underlying levels associated with the adaptation and self-realization of the subject of activity, and also determines its mental and physical specificity (Koteneva, 2019).

In the work of Pozdnyakov V. M. and Maltseva T. V., based on a meta-analysis of foreign and domestic publications, the connection between subjective vitality and spirituality in the aspect of personal security is revealed. Taking into account the reliance on the provisions of resource, situational-event and subject-being approaches, as well as the analysis of empirical research data on the manifestations of different types of personality resources and the role of subjectivity in life creation, the author's model of professional longevity among people of retirement age is substantiated (Pozdnyakov, Maltseva, 2025).

An important aspect of a teacher's ability to work is his interaction with digital environments. The use of the Internet and instant messengers in communication between teachers and other participants in the educational process not only facilitates many communication issues, but also leads to a number of difficulties and dangers that they may encounter in their professional activities (Veselovskaya Y.N., 2025).

Foreign studies focus on the problem of the impact of health on a person's ability to work. Italo Lopez Garcia notes that declining health with age can limit a person's ability to

work, increasing the likelihood of a mismatch between their ability to perform certain tasks and the minimum requirements for the job offered. Traditional health indicators are not sufficient to understand how a person's ability to meet job requirements affects labor force participation and retirement intentions (Italo Lopez Garcia, 2025).

Goryacheva E.V. in her dissertation describes in detail the medical and biological components (state of health, nutrition, physical activity, absence of bad habits, heredity, etc.) that determine the level of physical health as an important factor of professional longevity (Goryacheva, 2020).

In the studies of Gorbunova N.V. and Fetisov A.S., the identified risks of a psychoemotional state, self-regulation of behavior, self-attitude and interpersonal interaction with others actualize the phenomenon of «professional longevity» and form the basis of psychological health (Gorbunova, Fetisov, 2023).

Interesting are not only socio-psychological, but also sociological, age, and economic ones. Medical and other parameters that determine the length of a «working life». It has been established that the expected length of working life and the expected duration of a healthy working life are longer for men than for women. Working life expectancy at the age of 50 has been increasing since the mid-90s, and this increase was more pronounced among women, which reduced gender differences. Working life expectancy is shorter for people with low levels of education, representatives of lower occupational groups, people who are subjected to high physical exertion at work, people living in the most socially and economically disadvantaged areas, overweight or obese people, smokers, people who lead a sedentary lifestyle in their free time, and people with chronic diseases (Rahman Shiri, 2021).

The publications show that professions associated with lower life expectancy are characterized by a high proportion of indoor (rather than outdoor) work, sedentary work, and lack of social interaction. In general, career choice becomes a key lifestyle factor determining life expectancy, which affects medical care and retirement plans based on the profession.

Jobs requiring an increased level of health, all other things being equal, are preferred by men, young and healthy people with a relatively low level of education. Work that requires an increased level of health has little impact on health-related behavior, since income and investment in health largely compensate for each other, which means that the impact on health can be almost entirely attributed to the direct health burden associated with work. More advanced medical technologies encourage low-skilled people to spend most of their lives in jobs that require an increased level of health, and thus increase the health gradient due to

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education. A high level of well-being protects against unhealthy career choices (Italo Lopez Garcia, 2025).

Thus, on the one hand, we observe a significant number of studies aimed at studying aspects of psychological well-being in the context of professional longevity. At the same time, the problems of determining their subjective well-being and assessing psychological health by teachers of secondary schools, taking into account the differentiation of their age, remain important.

METHOD AND METATERIALS

The purpose of this study

The purpose of this study is to study the relationship between individual components of psychological health and professional longevity of teachers of educational institutions on a limited sample of respondents.

Sample

Men and women aged 24 to 65 years (average age 44 ± 1 year, 32 respondents, pilot study). The small sample size of the study is due to the fact that the problem stated in our study relates to confidential information that not all teachers are willing to disclose. Identifying problems with «psychological health» can stigmatize teachers and also negatively affect the prolongation of their contracts with educational organizations.

Research methodology

The empirical methods included: the Scale for Assessing Expected Retirement Age by T.N. Berezina; Self-Assessment of Psychological Age by K.A. Abulkhanova and T.N. Berezina; the Scale of Psychological Well-Being by K. Riff, adapted by N.N. Lepeshinsky. Methods of mathematical processing and analysis of the obtained data: descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, descriptive data analysis, analysis of variance with Fisher's exact test.

Research hypothesis

The study identified differences between different age groups of teachers on the following scales: positive relationships; autonomy; environmental management; personal growth; life goals; self-acceptance; and psychological well-being. As teachers gain more teaching experience, they begin to rethink their age. The older the teacher, the older they perceive themselves to be relative to their actual age.

RESULTS

In the context of the study of the relationship between the psychological health of teachers and professional longevity, we consistently applied the following methods: The scale of assessment of the expected retirement age by T.N. Berezina; Self-assessment of psychological age by K.A. Abulkhanova and T.N. Berezina; The scale of psychological well-being K. Riff adapted by N.N. Lepeshinsky; mathematical and statistical method - Spearman's criterion.

Our study was dominated by women, since, according to previous studies, they primarily form the core of the teaching staff of educational institutions. The number of women was 87%, while the men in the study were 13%

As for the age characteristics of the sample, it is important to note that the main group of respondents (58%) belonged to the 45-47 age group. This age is characterized by the peak of working age, the presence of a professional background and a reserve of cognitive opportunities for productive work. All respondents had higher professional education.

Figure 1. Quantitative ratio of teachers by gender (%)

In our study, the sample consisted of 87% of male teachers and only 13% of female teachers. This gender asymmetry is explained by the fact that in Russia the predominance of women in the field of education in Russian schools (the feminization of teaching) is associated with historical and social factors. In the 19th century, teaching became one of the first professions available to women, as it was considered a «natural extension» of their role as

educators and keepers of the hearth. A female teacher was perceived as a «mother» to all students, which corresponded to the patriarchal norms accepted at that time. (see Fig. 1).

Figure 2. The scale of assessment of the expected retirement age (Berezina T.N. methodology).

Within the framework of the methodology for assessing the expected retirement age (Berezina's method), teachers were distributed as follows: group 1 (below the norm) – 62%, group 2 (norm) – 27% and group 3 (above the norm) – 11%.

The first group is characterized by the fact that these people live in harmony with themselves and society (in terms of pension issues). Representatives of the second group feel tired of life, professional burnout, and the value of «freedom» may prevail.

The third group is characterized by a willingness to retire later, perhaps he has an interesting job that he likes, gives energy and gives meaning to life, perhaps he expects to make a career, which also takes time (see Fig. 2).

Figure 3. The scale of psychological well-being by K. Riff.

The scale of psychological well-being by K. Riff adapted by N. N. Lepeshinsky allows us to identify the level of psychological well-being Interpretation of the results: 0-323 points - low level of psychological well-being, 324-353 points - average level, 354 and above points - high level.

28% of respondents experience a high level of psychological well-being; the average level is 22% and the low level is 50% (see Fig.3).

Figure 4. Methodology of self-assessment of psychological age according to K.A. Abulkhanova and T.N. Berezina

Within the framework of the methodology of self-assessment of psychological age according to K.A. Abulkhanova and T.N. Berezina, the respondents can be divided into 2 groups: group 1 scored < 50 points (41%) and group 2 \geq 50 points (59%, see Fig.4).

After preparing an Excel spreadsheet with psychodiagnostic examination data for each research method using the Statistica statistical program, a descriptive analysis of the data was performed (that is, descriptive statistics were performed), based on the results of which it was decided to apply parametric calculation criteria, since the graphical representation of the data on each scale fit into the curve of the normal distribution, and the indicators of asymmetry and humpiness (excess) each diagnostic indicator did not exceed three acceptable errors (see tab.1).

Table 1: Descriptive statistics

	THE ASYMMETRY			EXCESS			The final decision on normality
	Asymmetry (module)	3x Asymmetry error Normal Kurtosis	Normality	Excess (modulus)	3x Excess Error	Normality	
The scale of assessment of the expected retirement age	0,24	1,24	yes	0,32	2,43	yes	yes
Positive relationships	0,19	1,24	yes	1,52	2,43	yes	yes
Autonomy	0,15	1,24	yes	0,60	2,43	yes	yes
Environment management	1,02	1,24	yes	2,31	2,43	yes	yes
Personal growth	0,59	1,24	yes	0,58	2,43	yes	yes
Goals in life	0,24	1,24	yes	0,86	2,43	yes	yes
Self-acceptance	0,21	1,24	yes	0,89	2,43	yes	yes
Psychological well-being	0,42	1,24	yes	0,91	2,43	yes	yes
Self-assessment of psychological age	0,21	1,24	yes	1,15	2,43	yes	yes

The study involved 32 people – teachers from metropolitan and regional schools aged from 24 to 63 years. According to the results of the preliminary testing, the sample was divided into two groups.: 1) 12 people who considered that their psychological age (self-assessment according to the methodology of K.A. Abulkhanova and T.N. Berezina) is lower than their biological age (passport age) and 2) 20 people whose psychological age is older than their biological age (see Fig. 5).

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Figure 5. The age of the comparison groups (average values).

The analysis of the data showed that the average age of teachers who subjectively assess themselves younger than the real age is 62-63 years. Those who rate themselves older are 57-58 years old.

Figure 6. Age periods of the study sample (%)

It is noteworthy that the peak of the subjective feeling of aging occurs in the period of 45-54 years, when, apparently, the mechanisms of professional burnout are triggered. At the same time, «second youth» or «second wind» is experienced by teachers at the pre-retirement or retirement age, when, apparently, there is an awareness of their right to retire with increasing work tension (see Fig.6).

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Figure 7. Comparative analysis of psychological well-being scales (primary results)

As can be seen in Figure 7, teachers who rate themselves younger have a higher psychological well-being index, primarily due to the environmental management scale.

Table 2: Differences between the two comparison groups

	SS (sum of squares)	df (degree of freedom)	F (Fischer's criterion)	p-level
Positive relationships	2745,6	1	9,0	<0,01
Autonomy	1884,2	1	10,0	<0,01
Environment management	4290,1	1	11,0	<0,01
Personal growth	2363,0	1	14,7	<0,01
Goals in life	2803,3	1	16,4	<0,01
Self-acceptance	1264,3	1	5,3	<0,01
Psychological well-being	4136,0	1	14,9	<0,01

It should be noted that statistically significant differences between the two groups were revealed on all scales of the methodology for assessing psychological well-being. The analysis of the obtained results allows us to confirm that the teaching staff aged 55-65 are distinguished by a higher level of emotionally warm relationships with colleagues and friends; they respond more productively and adaptively to various situations; they are able to correctly prioritize and balance personal and social interests; there is a tendency towards self-efficacy and the development of their own professional and personal potential; they have a high level of competence; they express positive self-esteem and self-confidence; they formulate more

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significant goals and are more meaningful and goal-setting in life; moderately expressed nonconformism; reliance on realism in all spheres of life (Table 2).

Table 3: Correlation analysis (Pearson)

	Self-assessment of psychological age
Age	0,35
	p<0,05

An important conclusion of the study remains the fact that over the years, teachers internally begin to overestimate their age, considering themselves to be older than the real age (Table 3).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The study shows that the average age of teachers who subjectively assess themselves younger than the real age is 62-63 years. Those who rate themselves older are 57-58 years old.

2. The time interval of subjective aging falls on the period of 45-54 years, possibly due to the onset of stages of professional burnout.

3. Teachers who rate themselves younger have a higher psychological well-being index, primarily due to the «environmental management» scale.

4. The differences between contrasting groups on the following scales are revealed: positive relationships; autonomy; environmental management; personal growth; goals in life; self-acceptance and psychological well-being.

5. As teachers increase their teaching experience, they begin to overestimate their age internally, considering themselves to be older than their real age.

The 45-54 age group in the teaching profession is the most vulnerable to the risks of professional longevity and burnout. Special training and recommendations for educational psychologists working with teachers are needed. An important task is the implementation of technologies aimed at increasing the professional longevity index, reducing tolerance for subjective psychological age, and improving teachers' psychological well-being. Psychotherapy programs can significantly reduce the risks of professional burnout and deformation.

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Research Statement

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest for the study.

Financial Support: This study was conducted as part of the «Risks and Resources of Teacher Longevity» project.

Ethical Approval: The design required all participants to voluntarily consent to participate in the research program. Each participant was interviewed beforehand, and consent was obtained for the interpretation of their data. The study was conducted anonymously and maintained a high level of confidentiality. The study was approved by the ethics committee.

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